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THESIS

Improving object classification accuracy in Digital Holographic Microscopy

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Thesis Proposal Form

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Thesis

Title: Improving object classification accuracy in Digital Holographic Microscopy

Summary of the thesis:

Digital Holographic Microscopy (DHM) is an emerging technology for classifying and counting cells and other microorganisms in biological samples in suspensions. A major advantage of the in-line DHM used in this project is that it allows volumetric imaging of samples with a relatively simple optical setup, thus reducing the need for sample preparation. Objects can be reconstructed in various focal planes using numerical methods, and the object in the resulting holograms can be classified using machine learning models. Due to the large variety of objects having diverse morphological properties, it is essential to capture as much information as possible for accurate classification. In this project, we explore various methods to obtain additional object information in order to enhance the classification accuracy of deep learning models. These may include bright-field/fluorescent imaging, various dyeing methods, or dynamic imaging.

Detailed task description:

Tasks:

- State-of-the-art study of various methods to enhance DHM classification accuracy
- Experimental measurements using selected methods
- Building and training deep-neural models using enhanced training data
- Evaluating and comparing results to those earlier models' trained on DHM-only measurements

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Declaration of Authenticity

I, undersigned Barbara Bicsák, student of the Faculty of Information Technology and Bionics at the Pázmány Péter Catholic University, hereby certify that this thesis was written without any unauthorized help, solely by me and I used only the referenced sources. Every part, which is quoted exactly or in a paraphrased manner, is indicated clearly with a reference. I have not submitted this thesis anywhere else.

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Abstract

Digital holographic microscopy allows volumetric imaging of rare suspensions, reconstruction of the focal plane of the suspended objects, and enables their automatic classification using machine learning algorithms. In this work, we focus on the classification of microorganisms suspended in liquids in the range of 2-100 micrometers. Due to the finite resolution of the mapping, classification based on morphology has limitations. The performance of classification is significantly impaired if the proportion of objects belonging to each class is imbalanced (e.g., a small number of organisms to be detected is accompanied by an order of magnitude more other inanimate objects, e.g. debris, in the sample.) Also due to limited resolution, the detection of small objects such as bacteria is difficult or not possible. Distinguishing between living and non-living organisms on holograms recorded by DHM is very difficult, as there is minimal morphological difference between them.

To overcome these problems, we have built an apparatus that simultaneously records holographic images of the field of view and can detect the autofluorescence emitted by the organisms on a separate imaging channel, as well as the fluorescence that occurs with a specific staining procedure. The subject of my master thesis is, on the one hand, the development of an appropriate staining procedure, which does not require extensive sample preparation, and thus can be automated in the future. On the other hand, the creation of a training database from the samples stained by the given procedure, and the evaluation of the algorithms trained by the databases. The structure of this diploma thesis is as follows: In the introduction, I put the work in context, and I also describe the structure of this work in more detail. Next, I introduce digital holographic microscopy (DHM) and state the problems I attempt to tackle in this work (limitations of classification based on morphology from images recorded by the DHM). Following I explore and plan the work ahead, with a particular focus on fluorescent staining/dyeing of the samples. I also explain how I achieved the desired goals and why I made certain choices. Furthermore, I detail my results gained by creating databases and training and evaluating

deep neural models with various input parameters including fluorescent information, and the answers to the core question of this work: does fluorescence/autofluorescence indeed improve the accuracy (precision, recall, etc.) of the classification. Finally, I briefly recap the assumptions, summarize the results, and lay out possible avenues for future work.

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Contents

Thesis Proposal	i
Declaration of Authenticity	v
Abstract	vi
Acknowledgements	viii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Structure of the thesis	2
2 Digital Holographic Microscopy and its applications	4
2.1 Principle of DHM	4
2.1.1 Advantages of DHM	5
2.1.2 Disadvantages of DHM	6
2.2 Digital holographic microscopes in the research laboratory	6
2.3 Potential applications	7
2.3.1 Monitoring of microalgae	7
2.3.2 Review of yeast detection in alcoholic beverages	8
2.3.3 Monitoring of drinking water	9
3 Machine learning algorithms in the DHM	11
3.1 Measures	12
3.1.1 Measures in imbalanced datasets	13
3.1.2 Confusion Matrix	14
3.2 Deep-learning	15
3.3 Convolutional Neural Networks	15
3.4 Supervised and unsupervised learning	17
3.4.1 Supervised algorithms	17

3.4.2	Unsupervised algorithms	17
3.5	Transfer learning	18
3.6	Generative Adversarial Networks	19
3.6.1	Application of Generative Adversarial Network in DHM	20
3.7	K-Fold Cross-Validation	21
3.8	Focal depth	21
3.9	Segmentation	22
3.10	Classification	23
3.11	Training epochs	23
3.12	Increasing the accuracy of DHM using different methods	24
4	Fluorescence microscopy	26
4.1	Principle of fluorescence microscopy	26
4.2	Advantages and limitations	27
4.3	Staining techniques used in fluorescence microscopy	28
4.3.1	Fluorescein Diacetate used in Fluorescence Microscopy	29
5	DHM-Brightfield, DHM-Fluorescence bimodal microscope	30
5.1	Creating the training database for cell viability	32
5.2	Creating the training database for imbalanced classes	33
5.3	Training deep neural models	34
5.3.1	Cell viability	34
5.3.2	Imbalanced classes	39
6	Results	44
6.1	Results in live-dead yeast cell detection	44
6.2	Results in imbalanced classes	47
7	Conclusions	50
8	Summary	52
8.1	Tasks	52
8.2	Achievements	52
8.3	Plans for future work	53
	References	59

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1. Background

The digital holographic microscopes in our research laboratory allow fast and automated analysis of large volume samples. The advantages of the DHM include the fact that it requires no sample preparation and no human interaction during the measurement, and the possibility to generate a three-dimensional image of the objects from the two-dimensional hologram by numerical back-propagation. After defining the focal plane of the objects in the acquired images one by one and segmenting the objects, it is possible to create training databases from different samples, so that automatic classification can be performed using a deep neural network during subsequent measurements. However, in order for this process to give good and accurate results, the samples of the training database must first be labeled, which involves a considerable amount of work. Ideally, these datasets should contain an even number of samples to be classified for each class, but this is often unrealistic and the database is unbalanced i.e. the sample distribution for classes is not uniform. In this case, the results of the classification algorithm will be distorted by this phenomenon and will underperform for the class containing much fewer training samples.

In order to improve the classification performance, members of the research team have developed a digital holographic microscope-fluorescence bimodal microscope that allows the acquisition of holographic and fluorescence images of the same area in a flow-through arrangement, thus combining the advantages of both methods. With this equipment, I created several training databases containing simultaneously acquired holographic and fluorescence images. I used these to study training on unbalanced datasets and to distinguish live and dead yeast cells.

In the evaluation, both for the unbalanced datasets and for the discrimination of live-non-viable cells, significant improvements were seen for models that received as input not only phase and amplitude, and mask but also the fluorescence information as input during training.

1.2. Structure of the thesis

Short summary of the structure of the thesis:

Chapter 2 - Digital Holographic Microscopy and its Applications This chapter describes digital holographic microscopy. Its principle of operation, advantages and limitations compared to conventional microscopes are discussed. I will continue by presenting the microscopes with different parameters available in the research laboratory and their possible applications.

Chapter 3 - Machine Learning Algorithms in the DHM In this chapter, I will introduce the basics of machine learning and discuss its applications. I will also discuss supervised and unsupervised learning, transfer learning and generative adversarial networks. I will explain how machine learning is applied to the Digital Holographic Microscope.

Chapter 4 - Fluorescence Microscopy In this chapter, I summarise the basic principle, applications and advantages of fluorescence microscopy over conventional light microscopy. I mention the most common staining techniques and the dye used in my thesis, Fluorescent Diacetate, and its advantages.

Chapter 5 - DHM-Fluorescence Bimodal microscope In this chapter, I present the bimodal microscope that has been developed. I will also explain the process of creating the training database.

Chapter 5 - Conclusions In this chapter, I discuss the evaluation of models both for unbalanced datasets and for the distinction between live-non-viable cells. For both purposes, 3 models with different inputs were trained to examine the improvement in results, each using 5-fold validation. The best models are selected and then compared based on the results obtained.

Chapter 6 - Future Plans In this chapter, I mention some future plans, development options, and possible areas of application.

Chapter 2

Digital Holographic Microscopy and its applications

Digital holographic microscopy (DHM) is a powerful imaging technique for obtaining microscopic images of objects in three dimensions (3D). It is based on the same principle as conventional holography, but instead of using a physical hologram, it uses a digital recording of interference patterns created by light that has passed through or been scattered by the object of interest. DHM has been used to take microscopic images of biological specimens in their natural environment, providing detailed 3D views of their structure and dynamics.

2.1. Principle of DHM

In DHM, the object is illuminated with coherent light and the scattered light is then collected by a charge-coupled device (CCD) or a complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS). The interference pattern created by the light scattered from the object is recorded digitally and then reconstructed using computer algorithms. The resulting image is a 3D image of the object. In an off-axis DHM system, one of the beams of light is the object beam, which is focused on the object. The other beam is the reference beam, which is focused on the hologram plane. When the two beams interact at the hologram plane, they create a pattern of interference which is recorded as a hologram. The interference pattern is dependent on the angle of the two beams, the wavelength of the light, the phase difference between the two beams, and the optical path difference. The interference pattern created by the two beams of light is converted into a digital image, which can then be used to analyze the object.

Digital holographic microscopy is a powerful imaging technique with a wide range of applications. It is used in medical imaging [1], materials science [2] and many other fields. It can also be used to observe the structure and dynamics of living cells. The technology is also used to study the behaviour of particles in liquids and to develop new optical materials [3].

There are two key types of digital holographic microscopy: in-line and off-axis arrangements. In-line arrangements are suitable for dilute water samples where one portion of the light passes through the specimen freely – acting as the reference wave – while the other portion scatters on the objects. The interaction of these beams results in an interference pattern in the recording plane. The image is then processed to reconstruct the digital hologram. The advantage of this configuration is that it can be easily implemented with minimal hardware requirements. However, due to optical aberrations, the resolution and quality of the image may be affected.

The off-axis arrangement is another type of DHM, where the incident laser beam is directed at an angle to the optical axis of the microscope [4]. This allows for more control over the illumination direction of the sample, allowing for further depth information to be acquired. It requires two laser beams and two detectors. The first beam is focused on the object, while the second beam is used as a reference beam. Both beams are then captured by the two sensors, which are placed at an angle relative to each other. This configuration results in greater image quality and resolution, as it reduces the effects of optical aberrations. Additionally, it allows for a greater depth of focus and a wider field of view than in-line DHM. However, it also requires more complex hardware setup, making it more difficult to implement.

2.1.1 Advantages of DHM

Digital holographic microscopy offers a number of advantages over conventional microscopes, providing a more powerful and accurate tool for imaging a wide range of samples. The primary advantage of DHM is that it is able to capture the entire 3D structure of an object with a single image. This means that the user can visualize the entire object from any angle and distance, providing a much more complete understanding of its structure and composition. Conventional microscopes require multiple images taken from different angles, which can be time-consuming and labor intensive if the sample is complex or contains multiple layers.

Another benefit of DHM is its ability to capture images without having to physically

contact the sample [5]. This is advantageous for fragile samples or those that must remain in their original environment. In addition, DHM eliminates the need for staining in order to visualize the sample, which can damage some types of samples. Finally, DHM can be used to measure displacement and deformation of objects in real time, which can be useful for monitoring the performance of structures and materials.

In conclusion, DHM provides a powerful tool for imaging and understanding a wide range of samples with a single image, with higher accuracy and resolution, without contact and without the need for staining. In addition, DHM can be used to measure dynamic processes in real time, providing an invaluable tool for research and industrial applications.

2.1.2 Disadvantages of DHM

The image quality of DHM is not as good as that of conventional microscopes. The resolution of DHM is limited by the wavelength of the light used and therefore is not as precise as that of conventional microscopes, which can be adjusted to provide higher resolution images. Additionally, DHMs are not capable of providing high contrast images as they rely on interference between two light beams, which can be affected by environmental factors such as dust or humidity.

2.2. Digital holographic microscopes in the research laboratory

The first microscope is designed to detect objects of approximately 5-75 micrometers. Depending on the density of the sample, two different cuvettes can be used, one with a thickness of 0.2 mm and the other 0.8 mm. Depending on which cuvette is used, a hologram can be made with either 0.12 μl or 0.48 μl of sample in the captured image. The sample density to be measured is 0-50 objects/hologram, which can vary depending on the size of the objects, allowing the measurement of more than 1 ml of sample per hour. This instrument has great potential for detecting objects in this size range, such as algae and yeast cells.

The other microscope is a large sample volume microscope for detecting large objects. The large sample volume microscope developed by our research laboratory is characterised by its ability to measure large volumes of diluted samples, up to nearly 160 l at a time. It can be used when the size of the objects to be examined in the sample is in the 20-300 μm

range. This instrument does not use optics, magnification is achieved by using different reconstructive and illuminating wavefields, so it can be used as a lens-free microscope to measure various worms, protozoa and other large objects.

2.3. Potential applications

2.3.1 Monitoring of microalgae

Microalgae are microscopic plants that live in both marine and freshwater environments. These tiny organisms have been shown to have incredible potential to solve some of the world's most pressing environmental, economic and health problems [6]. Microalgae are particularly important because of their ability to capture and store carbon dioxide and their potential to produce renewable energy and clean water. First, microalgae can capture and store carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Carbon dioxide is a major contributor to global warming and reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide is crucial to mitigating the effects of climate change. This process is called carbon sequestration [7]. Secondly, microalgae can produce renewable energy. Microalgae can be processed to produce biodiesel, a renewable form of energy that is less harmful to the environment than fossil fuels [8]. This biodiesel can be used to power vehicles, generate electricity, and for heating and cooling. Microalgae can also be used to produce biogas, a renewable energy source that can be used to generate electricity. Thirdly, microalgae can be used to produce clean water by treating wastewater [9]. This process can reduce water pollution and improve water quality suitable for human consumption. In addition, microalgae can be used to produce drinking water from sources such as saline or contaminated water.

Microalgae can be produced in several ways, including open ponds and photobioreactors. Open ponds are the most common and economical method of producing microalgae. These ponds are shallow, open-air tanks filled with water and nutrients and exposed to sunlight [10]. The microalgae grow in the ponds and can be harvested using a variety of methods, such as skimming, settling, or centrifugation. Open ponds are easy to maintain and can be used to grow several types of microalgae. However, they are prone to contamination and require high levels of nutrients and sunlight in order to maximize the yield. Photobioreactors are closed systems in which microalgae are grown under controlled environmental conditions [11]. Photobioreactors are better than open ponds for producing microalgae because they are more controlled environments. They allow for more precise control of the parameters that affect microalgae growth, such as temperature, light

intensity, pH, and nutrient levels. Photobioreactors also provide protection from contamination and predation, as well as more efficient harvesting of the algal biomass. In addition, photobioreactors are much smaller in size compared to open ponds, making them more suitable for small-scale production.

Continuous monitoring of microalgae in the reactors allows optimisation of growth conditions, ultimately leading to higher yields of the desired products. By monitoring the microalgae, the environment in the reactor can be adjusted to provide optimal conditions for the microalgae to grow quickly and efficiently [12]. For example, the temperature, light and nutrient levels can be adjusted to give the microalgae the best possible chance of thriving. In addition, the pH of the reactor can be controlled so that it is not too acidic or too alkaline for the microalgae to survive. All these factors are important for the successful growth of microalgae and by monitoring them continuously, the best possible conditions can be maintained at all times. In addition to optimizing the growth conditions, continuous monitoring of the microalgae in the reactors allows changes in the environment that could negatively affect the microalgae to be detected. For example, if the reactor becomes overcrowded, the microalgae may become stressed and produce less product. Therefore, it is important to monitor the microalgae population in the reactor to ensure that overcrowding does not develop. Finally, continuous monitoring of the microalgae in the reactors can also help to identify contaminants that may be present in the reactor [13]. Contaminants such as bacteria or viruses can have a negative impact on microalgae and the products they produce. By regularly monitoring microalgae, potential contaminants can be identified and removed before they have a chance to cause problems. Overall, continuous monitoring of microalgae in reactors is an important part of the algae production process. By monitoring the microalgae, the environment in the reactor can be optimized for the best possible growth, changes that may negatively affect the microalgae can be identified and corrected, and potential contaminants can be detected and removed.

2.3.2 Review of yeast detection in alcoholic beverages

Filtering the yeast in alcohol is an essential part of the beverage production process. Yeast plays a vital role in the fermentation process and is necessary for the conversion of sugar into ethanol, but it can also lead to problems if it is not filtered properly. If left unchecked, excessive yeast can lead to off-flavors and other problems that negatively affect both taste and quality [14]. Filtering out the excess yeast will ensure a cleaner tasting drink with fewer impurities that is more palatable to consumers. If too much yeast

remains after fermentation, when the yeasts in the mixture convert the sugars into alcohol, this leads at best to turbidity or sedimentation and at worst to off-flavours such as sulphur compounds (and reduced shelf-life) [15]. Therefore, proper filtration procedures should be applied as early as possible to prevent these undesirable ingredients from entering the consumer level products. This will help maintain product consistency batch after batch, while providing a better quality end result for consumers who purchase alcoholic beverages such as beer or wine that have been properly filtered before being canned ready for bottling. Secondly, filtering out excess yeast provides protection against spoilage organisms that would otherwise thrive in an environment where large amounts of yeast are present, as bacteria are able to break down complex molecules such as acetaldehyde that are produced during fermentation. By removing these micro-organisms through filtration, the risk of potential biological hazards posed by the consumption of contaminated alcoholic beverages is significantly reduced.

Therefore, the installation of efficient filters in production plants ensures the freshness of products without additional risk factors, thus allowing them to remain competitive in a market where strict food hygiene requirements apply.

In summary, although essential at the production stages - inappropriate handling/-filtering techniques can have serious consequences downstream in the production chain, resulting in finished products unfit for consumption and marketing.

2.3.3 Monitoring of drinking water

Worms in drinking water are a problem that can be of great concern to people. Worms, such as nematodes and flatworms, are microscopic organisms that live in soil and water. They can enter drinking water if the source is contaminated with sewage or animal waste containing worm eggs or larvae. This contamination can come from farms, septic systems, animal waste left on the ground by animals, or even human excrement flushed down the toilet [16]. When this contamination enters streams and rivers used as drinking water sources, it carries with it the worm eggs, which hatch in the new environment given sufficient time to mature - usually about two weeks, depending on temperature conditions, before the contamination enters the drinking water source. The presence of worms in drinking water is dangerous because their consumption can lead to gastrointestinal infections such as diarrhoea, nausea, cramps and fever [17].

Laboratory tests are required to detect worms in drinking water. The most commonly used test for this purpose is a screening technique called membrane filtration [18]. In

membrane filtration, a contaminated water sample is placed in a device containing a filter with pores small enough to allow only micro-organisms, such as worms, to pass through. After filtration, these organisms are collected on the other side and examined under magnification using microscopic techniques. This allows experts to identify the worm species present and estimate their abundance within the sample. Another method often used by laboratories is centrifugal sedimentation combined with flotation or sedimentation alone, depending on how large or small the organisms under study [19]. During centrifugal settling (or flotation), samples are spun at high speeds, causing heavier particles such as protozoa and worms to sink, while lighter material such as planktonic algae float in the upper layers or are expelled during the spinning cycles. This makes it easier for researchers to identify individuals under the microscope, as most individuals are separated from the debris-like material in the background, making observation more efficient.

Chapter 3

Machine learning algorithms in the DHM

Machine Learning (ML) is a subfield of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that focuses on the development of computer processes that can learn and modify their behaviour based on given data. The principles of machine learning are rooted in probability theory, statistics, linear algebra, calculus and optimisation techniques [20]. ML algorithms use so-called training datasets to train algorithms called "models", which then make predictions about unseen data.

These models can be supervised learning models or unsupervised learning models, depending on whether they have been given labels or not. Supervised learning requires labeled training examples where the input variables have already been associated with some label, while unsupervised learning does not require such labeling as it uses clustering algorithms to discover patterns in unlabeled data sets.

Supervised learning is the most commonly used method for machine learning, as it provides a simple way for computers to learn from previous experience. This makes the process much more efficient, as the model adapts quickly based on previously seen examples, thus eliminating the need for direct instructions at each step on what to change for optimal performance, such as accuracy, speed efficiency, etc. Machine learning is essentially based on three main principles: generalisation capability; inductive bias; and computational tractability - all of which work together to teach machines how best to respond when faced with unfamiliar inputs, taking into account prior knowledge gained through prior training [21].

Generalisation ability refers to the ability of machines to accurately recognise patterns between different types of input, i.e. for example, words that sound similar are correctly

identified despite small differences between them.

Inductive bias refers to how well the ML algorithm applies generalizations learned in one situation to another related but different problem domain.

Finally, computational tractability looks at how easily/quickly the computations required to complete the tasks can be done – generally, simpler approaches are preferred over more complex ones as they require less computational power, which means faster results overall.

3.1. Measures

Precision and recall are two of the most important metrics used in classification to evaluate model performance. Precision measures whether the model is able to correctly classify positive examples by giving the percentage of true positive examples within the total predictions produced by the model. In contrast, recall measures the percentage of true positive examples within the total true positive examples, in simple terms, whether the model is able to identify all positive examples in the data.

Both precision and recall range between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating better model performance. High accuracy indicates that the model makes fewer incorrect predictions and is more reliable. In general, accuracy above 70% is considered good. A high recall rate indicates that the model is better able to correctly identify positive outcomes. In general, a recall above 70% is considered good. When evaluating the performance of a machine learning algorithm, it is important to consider both accuracy and recall. If a model has a high accuracy and a low recall, it means that the model produces fewer incorrect predictions but misses many true positive results. On the other hand, if a model has low accuracy and a high recall, it means that the model makes more incorrect predictions but is able to detect more true positive outcomes.

F1 score is a type of metric used to evaluate models in machine learning. It is an important metric since it is a combination of precision and recall, and thus provides a better measure of accuracy than either of these metrics alone. The F1 score is a harmonic mean of precision and recall that is often used to measure the performance of a model. It is also known as the F-measure or F-score. The F1 score is calculated by taking the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and the formula for the it is as follows:

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot \textit{precision} \cdot \textit{recall}}{\textit{precision} + \textit{recall}} \quad (3.1)$$

The F1 score ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 representing the best possible score. A value of 0 means that the model has no precision or recall; a value of 1 means that the model has perfect precision and recall.

Test loss is an important concept in machine learning that refers to the amount of error in a machine learning model's predictions. Test loss is a measure of how well a trained machine learning model can generalize its knowledge to unseen data [22][Z. Bai 2014]. It is one of the main metrics used to evaluate the performance of machine learning models. In a nutshell, test loss measures the gap between the predicted labels and the ground truth labels of unseen data. For most machine learning tasks, it is recommended to divide the dataset into two subsets: a training set and a test set. The training set is used to train the model and the test set is used to evaluate the model's performance. During the training process, the model learns patterns from the training data and applies them to unseen data. Test loss is calculated by comparing the model's predictions with the ground truth labels from the test set. A lower test loss indicates that the model is better at generalizing its knowledge and making accurate predictions on unseen data. Conversely, a higher test loss indicates that the model is not able to accurately generalize its knowledge. The goal of model training is usually to minimize the test loss as much as possible.

3.1.1 Measures in imbalanced datasets

In machine learning, imbalanced data sets refer to data sets in which the number of samples in one class is significantly less than the number of samples in the other classes. This can lead to a model that is biased toward the majority class. This can lead to poor model performance and inaccurate predictions.

In machine learning, to prevent imbalanced data sets, various techniques can be used to produce balanced data sets using various techniques such as undersampling, oversampling, data augmentation, and ensemble methods. In undersampling, we randomly remove observations from the majority class to make the data set more balanced. Oversampling is the random duplication of observations from the minority class to make the data set more balanced. Ensemble methods combine several models to create a single model that is less likely to be biased toward the majority class. Data augmentation means creating synthetic data points that resemble the minority class.

Data augmentation is a technique that artificially increases the size of a data set by

creating synthetic data points similar to the original data set [23]. It has the advantage that it can help to rebalance unbalanced data sets and improve the performance of machine learning models. The disadvantage of data augmentation is that it can add noise to the data set, which can lead to overfitting or incorrect predictions.

The most commonly used augmentation methods include random crops, rotations, flips, and noise. In random cropping, images are randomly cropped into images of different sizes and aspect ratios [24]. Rotations involve the random rotation of images at different angles. Flips refer to random horizontal or vertical inversions of images. Color jitter refers to random changes in the brightness and contrast of images. Noise refers to the random noise enhancement of images.

3.1.2 Confusion Matrix

A Confusion Matrix is a tool used to evaluate the performance of a classification algorithm. It is a table that illustrates the performance of a classification model by examining the number of correct and incorrect predictions made by the model. It is used to measure the accuracy of a classifier in a binary classification problem. The confusion matrix is a 2x2 table that contains four outcomes produced by a binary classifier.

The 3x3 confusion matrix expands upon the 2x2 confusion matrix by adding an extra dimension. It is used to evaluate the performance of a classifier when dealing with three classes or categories, rather than two. For example, it could be used to evaluate a classification model that predicts whether an image contains a dog, a cat, or neither. The 3x3 confusion matrix contains nine outcomes produced by a three-class classifier.

The confusion matrix is composed of four main areas: true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). A true positive is a correct prediction that the instance belongs to the positive class. A true negative is a correct prediction that the instance does not belong to the positive class. A false positive is an incorrect prediction that the instance belongs to the positive class. A false negative is an incorrect prediction that the instance does not belong to the positive class.

The 3x3 confusion matrix contains nine cells, each representing one of the nine possible outcomes of a three-class classifier. The cells are labeled as follows: TP, TN, FP, FN, TP-1, TN-1, FP-1, FN-1, and FP-2. The TP cell represents the number of true positives, TN cell represents the number of true negatives.

The 3x3 confusion matrix can be used to evaluate a variety of metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Accuracy is the ratio of correct predictions to

the total number of predictions. Precision is the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false positives. Recall is the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false negatives. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

A 3x3 confusion matrix is a powerful tool for evaluating the performance of a classification algorithm. It can be used to measure accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. It can also be used to identify sources of misclassification and areas for improvement.

3.2. Deep-learning

Deep-learning is a branch of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks (ANNs) to understand patterns in data. It is a type of supervised learning, which means that a computer is presented with labeled sets of data to learn from. deep-learning has become popular in recent years because it can produce more accurate and reliable results than traditional machine learning techniques [25].

The basic principle of deep-learning is based on an artificial neural network (ANN), which consists of layers of interconnected nodes that process information in a similar way to the human brain and are able to recognise complex patterns in large data sets [26]. Individual nodes perform computations and send signals across the network, enabling predictive analysis and decision-making capabilities. By training the model on an input dataset, the weights of each layer are adjusted until satisfactory performance is achieved on the output set (the desired outcome). This process enables the use of deep-learning models in applications such as image recognition [27], natural language processing (NLP) [28], robotic control systems [29], and autonomous vehicles [30]. Deep-learning algorithms use multiple layers or "deep nets" that allow them to interpret complex relationships within data sets much faster than traditional methods; this makes them an effective tool for solving problems such as image recognition or accurately understanding natural language sentences, without relying heavily on pre-programmed rule sets like other AI approaches.

3.3. Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) used in computer vision and image recognition. CNNs use convolutional layers to process images, allowing them to extract features from an input image such as edges, shapes, and colors. This makes the network more efficient at recognizing patterns in images compared

to other ANN architectures such as fully connected networks or recurrent neural networks.

The first step for CNN is the Convolution Layer which applies a set of filters on an input image by sliding it across all spatial locations [31]. Each filter corresponds to a feature map that detects certain features from the original image like lines or edges. The output of this layer is called 'Feature Map' which can then be fed into further layers for extraction of semantic information like object detection.

The next layer is called Pooling Layer where the spatial pooling technique applied on feature maps generated by the convolution layers helps reduce noise while preserving important features from original images like shape and size. It also reduces dimensions so that processing time can be reduced without losing too much information. There are two types of pooling techniques: max pooling and average pooling each having its own advantages depending upon application needs.

Max pooling is a technique which selects the maximum value from a subset of the input. The advantage of this method is that it reduces the size of the input while still preserving the most important features of the data. This allows for a reduction in the number of parameters and faster training times. The disadvantage of max pooling is that it can be computationally expensive and can lead to overfitting of the data.

Average pooling, on the other hand, selects the average value from a subset of the input. Average pooling has the advantage of being less computationally expensive than maximum pooling and can often lead to better generalisation of the data. The disadvantage is that it may not be as effective in preserving the most important features of the data.

Afterwards comes Fully Connected Layers also known as Dense Layers where every neuron present in one layer is connected with every neuron present in the previous layer.

Fully connected layers are responsible for making predictions based on the input from the previous layer. They are often used for classification, regression, and other tasks. They can also be used to detect patterns in data, such as those generated by images or text. It is the most common type of layer in a neural network and is typically used in the final layers to generate the output.

3.4. Supervised and unsupervised learning

3.4.1 Supervised algorithms

Supervised learning is a type of machine learning algorithm where the model is trained on labeled data [32]. The labeled data consists of input variables or features and output variables that are used to train the model. The goal of supervised learning is to use the training data to produce an accurate predictive model that can be applied to unseen data to make predictions about future outcomes. Supervised learning algorithms include linear regression, logistic regression, decision trees, and support vector machines (SVMs).

Linear regression models are used to predict continuous outcomes such as house prices or stock returns from numerical input data such as population size or the number of shares outstanding [33].

Logistic regression models are used to predict discrete categories such as credit risk or customer churn from numerical inputs such as income level or number of days since last purchase [34].

Decision tree algorithms form rules to determine which class each observation belongs to based on input characteristics [35]; this approach can also be used to select characteristics when dealing with large data sets with many correlated predictors, as only those characteristics are selected that have a significant impact on the accuracy of the prediction.

Finally, support vector machines use nonlinear boundaries between classes in order to produce more accurate classifications than traditional linear methods; this approach works well when there are two classes to distinguish between, but there may be multiple levels within each class [36].

The primary advantage of using supervised machine learning techniques over unsupervised techniques is that it allows the relationships between the target variable and its associated predictors to be inferred without requiring prior knowledge of how they interact, which directly leads to greater understanding and insight into the data set.

3.4.2 Unsupervised algorithms

Unsupervised learning is a type of machine learning that searches for previously undiscovered patterns in a data set without labels and without prior training. It is also sometimes called "self-organising" or "discovery-based" learning, as it allows the algorithm to act on its own to identify previously unknown structures in the data [37]. Unsupervised algo-

gorithms are able to cluster data points based on similarities, detect outliers and anomalies, generate new features from existing ones, and compress information into concise representations - to name just a few applications.

The most common use cases for unsupervised learning are clustering and dimensionality reduction (DR) [38], [39]. Clustering is the clustering of similar items; DR aims to reduce the complexity of high-dimensional data sets by finding lower-order representations of them without losing too much information. For both tasks, a number of popular unsupervised algorithms exist: K-means clustering is perhaps one of the best-known approaches; hierarchical clustering creates clusters using nested subgroups; DBSCAN is density-based spatial clustering that works well for irregularly shaped clusters; t-SNE (t -distributed stochastic neighbor embedding) reduces high-dimensional space to two or three dimensions while preserving local distances between points so that they can be easily visualized. Other DR techniques include principal component analysis (PCA), independent component analysis (ICA), and non-negative matrix factorization (NMF), among others.

Unsupervised methods offer an alternative approach when the goal is only to understand the relationships between data rather than to classify them into predefined classes.

In addition, unsupervised models often require fewer resources than their supervised counterparts, as they do not require large amounts of labeled training samples and do not require expensive infrastructure, such as the powerful graphics processing unit needed for deep neural networks.

3.5. Transfer learning

Transfer learning is a machine learning technique that allows knowledge acquired from one model to be applied to another model [40]. The method was developed in response to the problem that there is a limited amount of labeled data available for training deep neural networks. Transfer learning can reduce the time and resources required to train new models on small data sets by transferring knowledge from an existing, pre-trained model. Transfer learning works by fine-tuning a pre-trained model on a new dataset with different labels or classes from those used in the original training process. To do this, the parameters of the pre-trained model are frozen so that they do not change during training, and only those layers where changes are desired are unlocked for further optimization using the backpropagation algorithm.

There are two main types of transfer learning: instance-based transfer (also known as

inductive transfer) and feature representation-based transfer (also known as transduction) [41]. In instance-based transfer, instances learned on one dataset are directly applied to another similar task, while in feature representation-based transfer, features learned in one domain are transformed into representations applicable to multiple domains or tasks.

Instance-based transfer learning is used when little or no labeled data is available, but unlabeled data exists for both source and target tasks. Here, all instances of the source task do not necessarily have to be exactly the same, but they must show some similarity to each other so that success on the source task can be replicated on the target task [42]. Despite the fact that there are few differences between them, this method helps save time and resources instead of having to create a complex network architecture.

Overall, transfer learning is now a widely accepted phenomenon as it has the potential to accelerate research progress, especially in areas related to deep neural networks where manual tuning of parameter values takes long periods of time, leading to increased complexity problems.

3.6. Generative Adversarial Networks

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are a type of deep-learning architecture that uses two neural networks competing against each other [43]. The idea behind GANs is to have one network, called the generator, generate new data instances while the second network, called the discriminator, evaluates them for authenticity. This competition between two networks can lead to better performance than traditional supervised learning methods as it allows for unsupervised training of both models simultaneously and encourages innovation within generated samples.

The most common use case for GANs is image generation – creating realistic images from noise or random vectors with no prior knowledge about the data set it was trained on. Generative models also find applications in video synthesis and natural language processing tasks such as text generation or summarization. In addition to these popular use cases, researchers have been developing more specialized models tailored towards certain tasks such as speech recognition or facial expression analysis [44].

At its core, a GAN consists of two components: A generator and a Discriminator which work together in an adversarial setting where one model tries to generate realistic examples while another tries to detect fraudulent ones based on real examples from some dataset. In most cases, the two competing networks are represented by multilayer neural networks consisting of either convolutional or fully-connected layers, or possibly both.

Fake samples should be detected with low probability values while real ones should be classified correctly (with high probability values). The generator updates its weights using gradient descent depending on feedback received from the discriminator's output so that the next time when same noise is used again then the generated samples will look more similar to those taken out of the dataset. Discriminator parameters are updated using a standard backpropagation algorithm based on the difference between expected probabilities assigned by itself and true labels associated with inputs provided by either dataset or the generator's output. After some number of iterations, both parts reach an equilibrium state where discriminating power reaches a maximum level at the same time when generated images become indistinguishable even for humans though still being fake since they were created without access to any external information about the underlying distribution contained inside source datasets during the training stage.

One of the advantages of using GANs is that they generate data that is indistinguishable from real data, which enables realistic applications [45]. They are also capable of learning from unlabelled data, making them more versatile than supervised learning algorithms. These networks can also be used to generate data that can be used for data augmentation, including images, text, and sounds.

3.6.1 Application of Generative Adversarial Network in DHM

An advantage of digital holographic microscopy over conventional microscopes is the possibility of three-dimensional (3D) reconstruction of volumetric samples from even one hologram, allowing more time-efficient measurement of larger volume samples. The quality of the reconstruction of holograms is affected by interference rings from twin-images or objects outside the focal planes due to missing phase information, but additional artifacts due to illumination can also appear. However, it is also possible to combine the advantages of bright-field microscopy and digital holographic microscopy using cross-modality deep-learning with GAN, thus eliminating distracting speckle and artifact patterns but allowing volumetric imaging [46]. This deep neural network performs a cross-modality image transformation, whereby a hologram digitally back-propagated at a given depth produces an image that corresponds to an image taken at the same depth but with a bright-field microscope. To be successful, the deep neural network has learned the statistical image transformation between images captured by the two systems of the same fields of view (FOV). With this combined imaging, the interference patterns characteristic of holograms can be eliminated, and volumetric bright-field images can be produced that

does not require mechanical scanning to be captured.

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) can be used to improve the digital holographic microscope in combination with the bright-field microscope by providing the ability to generate “synthetic” images of microscopic features that may be otherwise difficult to capture in the real world.

3.7. K-Fold Cross-Validation

K-Fold Cross-Validation was used to evaluate the models. K-Fold Cross Validation is a popular technique in machine learning used to evaluate the performance of a model on unseen data. It is a type of resampling technique that helps reduce bias in the model by dividing the data into k-folds and then training and testing the model on different folds [47]. This helps reduce the variance in the model and helps ensure that the model does not overfit the training data.

The K-Fold Cross Validation technique works by randomly dividing the data set into k-folds. Each fold serves as a test set and the rest of the data serves as a training set. The model is then trained and tested using different folds. The results of each run are then combined to give an overall estimate of the model performance.

The K-Fold Cross Validation technique has several advantages over traditional model evaluation techniques. First, it is more reliable than traditional methods because it uses multiple subsets of the data for evaluation. Second, it helps reduce model bias by training and testing the model on different subsets of the data.

3.8. Focal depth

Focal depth estimation is an important technique for image classification. It is used to determine the depth of field of an image and its relevance to the classification task. By estimating the depth of focus, the classifier can better distinguish between similar objects in the image. The focal depth estimation technique can be used to derive back to image classification. This is done by dividing the space into certain classes based on distance, into which the inputs are then classified. The database in this case is also manually created, in which the focus is randomly spread over a certain range and the object is then classified into the appropriate class.

3.9. Segmentation

For the object segmentation, a UNet-based mesh has been trained with heavy augmentation, which assigns values of 0 and 1 to the mask images associated with the objects, depending on whether the object or the background is located on the given pixel.

Heavy augmentation in image classification processes is the process of using a variety of techniques to significantly increase the amount of data used to train a machine learning model. This includes image augmentation, such as flipping, rotating, scaling, and cropping images, as well as adding noise, blurring, and applying various filters to images. Heavy augmentation can also involve collecting more data from additional sources and incorporating it into the dataset. This can significantly improve the accuracy of the model and help it generalize better.

UNet-based image segmentation is a deep-learning technique used to accurately segment images into meaningful parts. It is based on the U-Net architecture, which was first developed by Olaf Ronneberger, Philipp Fischer, and Thomas Brox in 2015 for biomedical image segmentation [48]. The architecture of U-Net consists of a contracting path (left side) and an expansive path (right side). The contracting path is composed of a series of convolutional and max pooling layers which gradually reduce the spatial size of the input image and extract image features. The expansive path is composed of a series of convolutional and transposed convolution (or deconvolution) layers which gradually increase the spatial size of the output and combine the extracted features to obtain a full segmentation of the image.

The contracting path is composed of a series of down-sampling layers which reduce the spatial size of the input image. The convolution layers extract features from the image while keeping the spatial size the same. The max-pooling layers are used to reduce the spatial size of the image, generally by a factor of two. These layers also reduce the amount of computation required and allow for more efficient feature extraction.

The expansive path is composed of a series of up-sampling layers which increase the spatial size of the output. The up-sampling layers are used to increase the spatial size of the output, generally by a factor of two. The convolution layers combine the extracted features to obtain a full segmentation of the image.

UNet-based image segmentation has been applied to a variety of tasks such as medical image segmentation, object detection, and image classification. It has proven to be a powerful tool for accurately segmenting images into meaningful parts and has become

one of the most popular deep-learning architectures. Masks are used in UNet-based image segmentation for accurately segmenting a given image into meaningful parts. A mask is a binary image where each pixel is assigned a value of 0 (background) or 1 (foreground). The mask is used to identify the objects in the image and separate them from the background. The UNet architecture uses a series of convolutional and max pooling layers to extract features from the input image. These features are then used to generate a mask for the image. The mask is then applied to the image to separate the objects from the background. The generated mask is then used as an input to the expansive path of the UNet architecture. The expansive path consists of a series of up-sampling layers which increase the spatial size of the output and combine the extracted features to obtain a full segmentation of the image. Masks are an important part of UNet-based image segmentation as they allow for accurate segmentation of an image into meaningful parts. Masks allow the UNet architecture to identify the objects in the image and separate them from the background.

3.10. Classification

Image classification is performed using a convolutional network and a fully connected network, where a convolutional network is first used to extract features of the input image. This is done by applying convolutional filters to the image to detect certain features such as edges and shapes. This is followed by a pooling layer that reduces the size of the feature map and helps to reduce the number of parameters in the network. The output of the convolutional network is then fed to a fully connected network that classifies the image based on the features extracted. After learning the relationships between the features extracted from the image and the classes to be identified, the output of the fully-connected network is a prediction of the class regarding the input image.

3.11. Training epochs

Epoch in machine learning is a term used to describe a single pass of all the training data through a machine learning algorithm. An epoch can be thought of as a single iteration of training, where the model is presented with a set of training samples, and the model is updated accordingly [49]. This process is then repeated until the model converges, which is when the model reaches a point where the predicted output is as close as possible to the actual output.

The number of epochs that are required for convergence depends on the size of the training data and the complexity of the model. The more complex the model is, the more epochs it will require to reach convergence. In addition, the more data that is available, the more epochs are likely to be needed. Generally, the number of epochs required to achieve convergence ranges from 10-100, depending on the size and complexity of the data.

During each step of an epoch, the model is updated in a process known as backpropagation. This is where the model takes the input data, runs it through its layers of neurons, and then produces an output. The output is then compared to the actual output, and the weights of the neurons are adjusted accordingly. This process is repeated until the weights of the neurons are such that the output of the model is as close as possible to the actual output.

3.12. Increasing the accuracy of DHM using different methods

Data augmentation is a technique that can be used to artificially create additional training data. By applying various transformations such as rotation, mirroring, shifting, and cropping, more data can be generated which can improve the accuracy of the model [50]. Ensembling is another technique which involves combining multiple models to create a more accurate prediction [51]. This can be done by combining different models that have been trained on the same data, or by combining models that have been trained on different data.

Feature engineering is the process of selecting and transforming the best features from raw data to create a more accurate model [52]. This involves selecting the most important features, transforming them, and then adding new features to the model. Regularization is a technique used to reduce the complexity of a model, which can help to prevent overfitting and improve accuracy. This is done by adding a regularization term to the cost function of the model. Finally, hyperparameter tuning is the process of searching for the optimal values of the various hyperparameters of a model to achieve the best performance. This can be done using various algorithms such as grid search and random search.

These methods can be combined to create a powerful model that is capable of achieving high accuracy. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of these methods

will depend on the data and the task at hand. Therefore, it is important to experiment with different methods and find the best combination for a particular task.

Chapter 4

Fluorescence microscopy

Fluorescence microscopy is a type of optical microscopy that uses fluorescence and phosphorescence to image the structures of living cells and other microscopic objects. Fluorescence microscopy is widely used in biological research as it allows researchers to observe the details of cellular architecture and function in real time. This method can also be used to study biochemical processes, such as protein-protein interactions, enzyme kinetics, and gene expression. This technique has made it possible to visualize cellular components and molecules in unprecedented detail and has revolutionized the life sciences. By using the appropriate fluorescent dyes, it is possible to selectively label specific components of a cell or tissue, such as proteins or organelles, and then visualize them under the microscope.

4.1. Principle of fluorescence microscopy

The fluorescence microscope is a powerful tool for studying the structure, function and behaviour of cells and molecules, as well as organelle structure, protein distribution, cell division and differentiation dynamics, and cell behaviour in response to external stimuli [53]. It uses fluorescent dye molecules that absorb light at a certain wavelength and then emit a longer wavelength, allowing the labelling of biological samples. Fluorescence microscopy allows researchers to gain greater insight into the complexity of biological systems and provides information that is not available with other techniques.

The principle of fluorescence microscopy is based on the phenomenon of fluorescence. Fluorescence occurs when a substance absorbs light of a certain wavelength (excitation light) and emits light of a different wavelength (fluorescence). In fluorescence microscopy, the fluorescent molecules are typically attached to or incorporated into the specimen, and the specimen is illuminated with an excitation light source. The excitation light is

absorbed by the fluorescent molecules, causing them to emit fluorescence. The emitted fluorescence is then detected and used to visualize the specimen.

The Stokes shift, named after its discoverer George Stokes, is a phenomenon observed in fluorescence microscopy [54]. It is the energy difference between the absorbed photon and the emitted photon. When a molecule is excited by absorbing a photon, the energy of the absorbed photon is greater than that of the emitted photon. This energy difference is called the Stokes shift. The Stokes shift is an important factor in fluorescence microscopy as it is responsible for the selective excitation of fluorophores. When an incoming photon of a given wavelength is incident on a fluorophore, the energy of the absorbed photon is transferred to the fluorophore and excites it to a higher energy state. The excited molecule then returns to its ground state by releasing a photon. However, the energy of the released photon is lower than the energy of the absorbed photon, resulting in a Stokes shift. The Stokes shift is also responsible for the emission spectrum of the fluorophore. Since the energy of the emitted photon is lower than that of the absorbed photon, the emitted photon has a longer wavelength than the absorbed photon.

The components of a fluorescence microscope fall into three main categories: the light source, the objective lens and the detection system. The light source typically consists of a mercury vapour, xenon or LED lamp that emits light at a specific wavelength. The role of the objective lens is to focus the light onto the sample. The detection system typically consists of filters, shutters and a detector such as a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera or photomultiplier tube (PMT).

Fluorescence microscopy is used in a wide range of scientific applications. One such area is cell biology, where it is used to study the localisation of proteins, nucleic acids and other molecules. It is a useful tool for biochemistry, for example to determine the interactions between proteins and other molecules [55]. In the case of drug development, it can be used to study the interactions between different drug molecules and their targets [56].

4.2. Advantages and limitations

The advantages of this method include the ability to visualise cellular components and their structures in great detail and to visualise them simultaneously, even with different dyes. As the method is sensitive, it can detect even very low concentrations of molecules, allowing the analysis of a single molecule.

The limitations of fluorescence microscopy include the fact that in most cases it

requires fluorescent probes, which can be toxic to cells, and that they often lose their fluorescence when illuminated, a process known as photobleaching.

4.3. Staining techniques used in fluorescence microscopy

Staining techniques are an essential part of fluorescence microscopy, allowing microscopic structures to be visualised and analysed. By selectively targeting specific molecules or organelles in a sample, staining can be used to identify different characteristics of cells and tissues.

The use of fluorescent materials allows the visualisation of cellular components in a highly specific way. These can be proteins (green fluorescent protein), antibodies or dye molecules, which can be used to detect not only proteins, but also nucleic acids and various organelles in cells, as well as to perform various functional assays.

Acridine Orange is a fluorescent dye that is commonly used to study DNA and RNA [57]. It binds to double-stranded nucleic acids, and its fluorescence can be used to measure the amount of DNA or RNA present in a sample. Acridine Orange has also been used to distinguish between living and dead cells, making it a useful tool for evaluating cell survival and viability.

Hoechst 33258 is a fluorescent dye used to study the structure of DNA [58]. This dye binds specifically to the major groove of DNA, and its fluorescence can be used to visualize the structure of the DNA molecule.

Bromophenol Blue is a dye that binds to proteins and is used to measure the amount of protein present in a sample [59]. This dye is widely used in electrophoresis and can be used to distinguish between different proteins based on their charge and size. Bromophenol Blue also has the ability to fluoresce when exposed to visible light, allowing for the visualization of proteins in a sample. It is also relatively cheap and easy to use, making it a popular choice for the detection of proteins.

Calcofluor White is a fluorescent dye used to study the structure of carbohydrates and other polysaccharides [60]. This dye binds specifically to cellulose and chitin, and its fluorescence can be used to visualize the structural components of these polysaccharides. It is also non-toxic and relatively inexpensive, making it a popular choice for research and clinical applications.

DAPI is a fluorescent dye used to study the structure of DNA [61]. This dye binds specifically to the minor groove of DNA, and its fluorescence can be used to visualize the structure of the DNA molecule.

Ethidium Bromide is a fluorescent dye used to detect and quantify DNA and RNA [62]. This dye binds specifically to double-stranded nucleic acids, and its fluorescence can be used to measure the amount of DNA or RNA present in a sample.

Pacific Blue is a fluorescent dye used to study the structure of proteins and other biomolecules [63]. This dye binds specifically to amino acids, and its fluorescence can be used to visualize the structure of proteins and other biomolecules.

PicoGreen is a fluorescent dye used to detect and quantify DNA and RNA [64]. This dye binds specifically to double-stranded nucleic acids, and its fluorescence can be used to measure the amount of DNA or RNA present in a sample .

SYBR Green is a fluorescent dye used to quantify DNA and RNA [65]. This dye binds specifically to double-stranded nucleic acids, and its fluorescence can be used to measure the amount of DNA or RNA present in a sample .

4.3.1 Fluorescein Diacetate used in Fluorescence Microscopy

Fluorescein diacetate (FDA) is a fluorescent dye commonly used in fluorescence microscopy to visualise living cells and tissues [66]. Fluorescent dyes are able to absorb light at one wavelength (490 nm) and emit it at another wavelength (520 nm), resulting in a clearly visible contrast between the observed specimen and the background. The FDA is a particularly useful tool for studying cellular processes such as cell division or apoptosis, as its fluorescence can be monitored over time with minimal damage to the sample. Furthermore, because it does not bind specifically to any cell membrane, FDA allows researchers to study many different cell types without first having to label them with specific antibodies or other probes. When FDA is used for imaging purposes, it must first be introduced into the sample by incubation or injection; once inside the desired cells, it binds non-specifically to the cell membranes through hydrophobic interactions.

After binding, the excitation light causes a conformational change in the molecule, resulting in the emission of fluorescent light, which can then be detected by microscopy equipped with filters capable of separating the excitation and emission wavelengths. The intensity of the signal emitted depends on the amount of FDA taken up by each cell, so that differences between cells can be easily seen at high magnification, facilitating quantification. Its low toxicity also makes it suitable for working directly on human tissue samples.

Chapter 5

DHM-Brightfield, DHM-Fluorescence bimodal microscope

The bimodal microscope consist of a color bright-field microscope, and a monochrome holographic microscope sharing the same field of view. The sample is placed in a fixed cuvette of depth between 20-60 microns shown in Figure 5.1. The purpose of this device is to provide additional information compared to the holographic image for labeling/annotating a training database for deep learning. Holographic image has a limited resolution at the focal plane of objects of interest, partly because the raw hologram (from which it is being reconstructed) recorded by the camera's sensor contains information describing the whole volume (rather than just of the focal plane), and also because of missing phase information, reconstructed images are obstructed by the interference patterns of the twin images. In contrast, the bright-field image will contain all information attainable at this resolution, as well as color information also missing from the holograms. Other uses include the creation of a training database for GAN models for bright-field reconstruction (creation of bright-field-like images from reconstructed holograms), detecting specific staining/dyeing, and training phase reconstruction for holograms. There are a number of trade-offs introduced by this setup: As the bright-field and holographic microscopes have the same magnification, the depth of field (where objects are in focus) for the bright-field microscope is in the range of 3-4 microns. Since even the thinnest cuvette is at least 20 microns, the focus of the bright-field microscope must be adjusted manually. Fortunately, we have accurate estimates of the objects's focal depth from the hologram, so focusing can be automated using a precision motor on the z-axis. While In flow-through cells

Figure 5.1: Bright-field and DHM bimodal microscope

static contamination of the cuvette or optics can be eliminated from the image but by subtracting the averaged background, using a fixed cuvette this can be only achieved by moving the cuvette (and even this will not eliminate the contamination of the cuvette). This also has the additional benefit of multiplying the field of view. Therefore, for future versions, an x-y-z motorized platform will be required.

Replacing bright-field illumination with fluorescent illumination and adding an emission filter, we can build a bimodal fluorescent/holographic microscope shown in Figure 5.2. Its purpose is to detect fluorescent objects. The fluorescence can come from auto-fluorescence or some special staining, e.g. FDA live-inanimate detection or chlorophyll auto-fluorescence. Accurate focusing can usually be solved, but it is a time-consuming task. Fluorescence can also be detected with a small defocus, and then the reconstruction of the holographic image can provide the morphological details of the detected object. Multiple fluorescent lighting can be used and different objects can be well separated.

There are imaging techniques that combine digital holographic microscopy with fluorescence microscopy.

One such imaging technique is the combination of DHM and fluorescence microscopy, with potential applications in biomedical research, materials science, and nanotechnology [67]. The advantages of the technique include high-resolution imaging, simultaneous

Figure 5.2: Bimodal Fluorescent/holographic microscope

acquisition of phase and fluorescence properties, and the ability to detect weak signals. In a similar study, the simultaneous application of the two techniques was used to detect changes in refractive index, which is important for studying cellular processes, as well as morphology and cell density [68]. The system offers high resolution and sensitivity compared to conventional microscopy.

Another technique combines DHM with epifluorescence microscopy in order to monitor cell volume regulation [69]. This offers the possibility of high-resolution imaging of cell membrane structure while providing information on cell volume. In another case, this hybrid technique was used to study the dynamics of intracellular ion concentrations, which can provide important information in the fields of drug discovery and biophysics [70].

However, difficulties arise in the precise alignment of the optical components, the possibility of optical aberrations due to interference between the two imaging techniques, and the need for a high-sensitivity detector and a high-quality optical system.

5.1. Creating the training database for cell viability

Prior to this thesis, our group had also worked on live-nonviable studies of unstained yeast samples using phase and amplitude images segmented from holograms, which showed promising results and were supported by the results of training with fluorescent

samples. The average fluorescence value of the object was multiplied with the mask.

The first step of the measurement is to take an arbitrary number of holograms from the selected sample. During the process, the objects are brought into focus one by one on the acquired holograms, followed by segmentation to create a phase and amplitude image for a given object, and in the case of a bimodal microscope, a fluorescence image. In my current work, however, it is not the image that is used for training, but the average of the fluorescence signal in the image.

I used *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, or yeast cells, to distinguish live from dead cells. I chose this method because one of the most important tasks in beer and wine testing is the detection of yeast cells in the finished product, and it is easy to handle, does not settle during measurement, and can be used for a long time.

First I took some pictures of the yeast cell sample using light microscopy. I then stained 1 ml of this sample with 1 ml of methylene blue to see if there were any living cells in the sample. This method is the most commonly used viability test for yeast. The majority of the cells were indeed alive, only 1-2% were non-viable, i.e. that was the percentage of stained cells.

Then I split this sample in two and added ethanol to one of them and let it stand for 15 minutes. Meanwhile, I stained the sample containing live yeasts with FDA, adding 5 ml of yeast sample to 5 μ l of FDA stock solution. I then made holograms followed by annotation. After measurement, the software determined the average green fluorescence value in the segmented image for each object, which was used to determine whether objects with values above a certain value were live yeast and the rest were debris. Once the live yeasts were classified, I stained the previously ethanol-mixed sample with methylene blue at the 1:1 ratio described above to make sure that the yeasts were indeed no longer alive. I captured the staining result with a bright-field microscope, which clearly shows that nearly 100% of the cells were stained. I then also took holograms of this sample and annotated the resulting images into debris and dead yeast classes.

5.2. Creating the training database for imbalanced classes

To create the unbalanced dataset, I used *Scenedesmus subspicatus* (Sco) algae and yeast cells. The chlorophyll in Sco causes it to autofluorescence, which is easily visualized with the filter we used, while the yeast will not be detectable in the fluorescence image.

For this process, I chose Sco algae because when studying living water or algae reactors, there may be a case where we need to find the cells of interest among a lot of

interfering debris or non-living cells. The yeast is between 5 and 10 μm in size, while the algae of choice is between 5 and 13 μm , so it is often not possible to distinguish them at a glance in the reconstructed holograms taken by the holographic microscope.

For the holograms, I used two different samples: the first with a 1:2 ratio of yeast to algae, and the second with a 1:20 ratio, reducing the chance of the neural network learning the background of the images. In the annotation, however, I was already working with images from both measurements, thus the final data set included a mixture of samples from both measurements.

The Loss function used was Cross Entropy Loss. Cross entropy loss (also known as log loss) is a widely used loss function in Machine Learning and Deep Learning that measures the performance of a classification model whose output is a probability value between 0 and 1. It measures the difference between predicted and actual probabilities of a given data point. The goal is to minimize the cross entropy loss to improve the model's accuracy.

5.3. Training deep neural models

In both cases, 3-3 training runs were conducted, each of which included 5-fold cross-checking. The runs were trained with the following information: in the first case, only the amplitude (Fig. 5.3) and phase images (Fig. 5.4) were used as input, in the second case, the mask (Fig. 5.5) was added in addition to these, and finally, in the last case, not only the amplitude, phase, and mask (Fig. 5.6), but also the fluorescence information was included as input. The three best models were finally compared according to their different metrics.

5.3.1 Cell viability

First, I selected the best model from the run that received as input only the amplitude and phase images, i.e. only these could be used to try to distinguish between living and non-living cells. Based on the results of the confusion matrix in Figure 5.9, Model 4 had the most promising performance, however, it is clear from the loss function that the value associated with this model is by far the highest compared to the others, which means that its predictions are far from the actual values of the test data, i.e. it does not perform well on unknown data. This was also supported by the slightly lower F1 score in Figure 5.7 associated with it than the others, which could also mean that it over-fits the training data or does not generalise well to the test data. According to the loss function

Figure 5.3: Amplitude

Figure 5.4: Phase

Figure 5.5: Mask

Figure 5.6: Fluorescence
signal

values in Figure 5.8, Model 5 outperforms the others on the test data, but the confusion matrix clearly shows that it predicts incorrectly for live yeast much more often than the others. Since neither the F1 score nor the loss function showed any significant difference for the remaining three models, I selected Model 3, which produced the best results in distinguishing live and dead cells, based on the confusion matrix.

I then examined the results of a run whose input included the mask in addition to the amplitude and phase images. The mask contains information about the position of the object in the image by assigning a value to it: the background value is 0 and the object value is 1. Compared to the confusion matrix of previous models in Figure 5.10, the mask helps somewhat in distinguishing live and dead yeast cells, but the improvement is not very significant. The F1 score values of the models in Figure 5.11 in this run are approximately the same, but even in this case, it is not possible to draw any far-reaching conclusions based on this value. For the loss function values, shown in Figure 5.12, however, differences are already visible, with models 1, 3, and 4 appearing to be promising, while higher values for models 2 and 5 indicate that they could not perform effectively on unknown data compared to the others. Knowing these metrics, models 2

Figure 5.7: F-score of models trained only amplitude and phase for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.8: Loss function of models trained only amplitude and phase for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.9: Confusion matrix of models trained only amplitude and phase for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.10: Confusion matrix of models trained with mask for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.11: F-score of models trained with mask for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.12: Loss function of models trained with mask for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.13: Confusion matrix of models trained with additional fluorescence signal for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.14: F-score of models trained with additional fluorescence signal for live-nonviable cell detection

Figure 5.15: Loss function of models trained with additional fluorescence signal for live-nonviable cell detection

and 5 performed nicely based on the confusion matrix, but had the worst loss function values and were discarded for this reason. Of the remaining three models, I finally chose number 4, which had one of the best loss function values and also performed relatively poorly in the confusion matrix.

Finally, I evaluated the runs with fluorescence data, which was the average green fluorescence signal found in the images. As with the previous runs, as shown in Figure 5.14 there was no significant difference in F1 scores in this case. In this case, however, the loss functions in Figure 5.15 showed a very large variance: the best value was 0.089, which belonged to Model 4, while the worst result was 0.137 for Model 1. The confusion matrix shows in Figure 5.13 that live yeast was correctly predicted by all models except Model 5 in 99% of the cases, from which it can be concluded that fluorescence information contributes greatly to the correct classification of live yeast cells. While the loss function showed Model 4 to be promising, looking at the confusion matrix, it can be seen that it predicted debris as dead yeast most of the time. When comparing the values, I chose Model 3 because both the loss function value and the results from the confusion matrix were promising.

5.3.2 Imbalanced classes

In this case also, 5 models were first trained with the single amplitude-phase pair. As can be seen in Figure 5.17, all of the F1 scores except for model 3 had values between 0.918 and 0.932, while this one had only 0.904, i.e. a lower accuracy on the test data than the others. Also, Model 3 had the highest loss function value, shown in Figure 5.18 i.e. it did not perform well on the test data. Although the low loss function value of Model 4 was a good sign, it can be seen from the confusion matrix in Figure 5.16 that it often predicted the algae to be yeast, along with Models 2 and 5. Finally, I chose Model 1 because it mispredicted samples belonging to the yeast and algae classes in roughly the same number of cases, 7-8% of the time, compared to the other models, which mispredicted true yeasts as algae less often, but predicted Sco cells as yeast more often, 9-10% of the time.

In the next step I evaluated the models with masks as input. As shown in Figure 5.19, among the F1 scores, model 1 had the best result (0.930) and model 5 had the worst result (0.900). In terms of the loss function in Figure 5.21, these two models also performed the best and the worst: while model 1 performed outstandingly well (0.252),

Figure 5.16: Confusion matrix of models trained only on amplitude and phase for unbalanced training datasets

model 5 performed poorly (0.375), along with model 2. Models 3 and 4 were in between these two models in terms of performance, both in terms of F1 score and loss function. Based on the confusion matrix shown in Figure 5.20, I finally chose Model 1 because although its overall performance is not much different from the others, it can perform much better on unknown data not seen before.

In the case where fluorescence information from the images of the objects was also available as input, the results were promising. The total number of mispredicted events on the confusion matrix, shown in Figure 5.23 was noticeably reduced after providing fluorescence data. However, a significant difference can be observed in the plot of the loss function values in Figure 5.24: the two models mentioned above had the lowest values (0.108-0.109), which means that they are able to generalise most efficiently, i.e. to classify previously unseen samples into the correct classes. From the run, I chose Model 1 for comparison because although Model 3 also showed similar results, the one I chose predicted debris as yeast less often.

Figure 5.17: F-1 score of models trained only on amplitude and phase for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.18: Loss functions of models trained only on amplitude and phase for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.19: F-1 score of models trained with amplitude, phase, and mask for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.20: Confusion matrix of models trained with amplitude, phase, and mask for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.21: Loss function of models trained with amplitude, phase, and mask for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.22: F-1 score of models trained with amplitude, phase, mask, and fluorescence signal for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.23: Confusion matrix of models trained with amplitude, phase, mask, and fluorescence signal for unbalanced training datasets

Figure 5.24: Loss function of models trained with amplitude, phase, mask, and fluorescence signal for unbalanced training datasets

Chapter 6

Results

I used the following experimental setup to quantify the effect of various training inputs: To distinguish between live and dead cells in the yeast sample, I selected three differently trained models with increasing amounts of information as input: the first training had only the amplitude and phase images, the second had the mask of the segmented objects, and the third had all the above mentioned, with the addition of fluorescence values (average normalized brightness of pixels in the fluorescent channel within the ROI of the particular object). I used k-fold ($k=5$) validation on the training datasets. The following measures have been calculated for each validation: confusion matrix, loss function, F-score, accuracy, and precision. When comparing the three models, the improvement in the performance of the fluorescence model over the other two models is striking even at the level of individual measures, but it is important to examine them in combination to draw far-reaching conclusions.

6.1. Results in live-dead yeast cell detection

To distinguish between live and dead cells in the yeast sample, I selected three differently trained models with increasing amounts of information as input: the first training had only the amplitude and phase images, the second had the mask data, and the third had all the above mentioned, with the addition of fluorescence values. The results of distinguishing between living and non-living cells in the yeast sample are clearly shown in the figures comparing the three different models.

The plot of accuracy in Figure 6.1 shows that the model trained with fluorescence information has the highest value (0.956), while the models trained with mask and amplitude-phase image pairs only produced significantly lower results (0.899 and 0.906,

Figure 6.1: Accuracy of trained models for live-dead yeast cell discrimination

Figure 6.2: F-score of models trained to distinguish live-dead yeast cells

respectively). This means that the model trained with fluorescence values is 5% better at predicting the correct classes.

There is also a significant difference in the plot of the Loss function values in Figure 6.3: the fluorescent model has the smallest value (0.102), which means that it performs well and can accurately predict the desired outputs as a function of the input values. The low value also indicates that the model can generalise the data to perform well for unknown data. The other two models perform similarly for unknown samples (model using only amplitude and phase: 0.215, model using the mask: 0.247), indicating that the mask does not carry any additional information for prediction. As can be seen in Figure 6.2, for the F1 score, the model with the fluorescence value is the best performing (0.961), performing almost 6% better than the other two models (0.909, 0.915).

The confusion matrix in Figure 6.4 of the three models supports the previous promising results. It can be seen that the fluorescence model predicts only 0.05-1% of live and dead yeasts, which reached 27% for the other two models. This represents a significant

Figure 6.3: Loss-function of models trained to distinguish live-dead yeast cells

Figure 6.4: Comparison of the three best performing models with a confusion matrix

improvement. It is noticeable that dead yeast is also predicted as debris only 3% of the time, while live yeast is correctly classified 99% of the time, providing a reliable method for future measurements.

An interesting observation is the number of epochs required to teach each model. The model using mask needed the least, which was 29 epochs in numerical terms. The model using amplitude and phase required slightly more, 40, and the model using fluorescence information required the most, 64. From this, it can be concluded that the model with the most information took more time to learn the patterns in the data, but as the previously presented results show, it produced the best predictions.

6.2. Results in imbalanced classes

Figure 6.5 shows that when comparing the three best models trained on the unbalanced data set of algal and yeast cells, the accuracy increased by 7% compared to when only the amplitude and phase information was used as model input. Interestingly, while the mask did not provide any additional information for yeast cells, the accuracy improved by 2% when using it alone to discriminate between *Scenedesmus* and yeast. This might indicate that the network uses morphology information derived from the masks to improve predictions.

Furthermore, as shown in Figure 6.6, the Loss value has been reduced by a third (0.108) compared to the initial condition (0.307), which means that the autofluorescence prediction is much better on test data that are not yet known than the performance of the simplest model. The training that had the mask in this case also showed better results compared to the original model, but it only gave 5% better results.

The F1 score also shows an improvement for the fluorescent model in Figure 6.7, by 4% compared to the model trained with masks and by 6% compared to the simplest model. This means that this model is better at predicting true positives and avoiding false negatives.

The preceding experiment's conclusion was the fact that the fluorescent model, although it performed very well on the test data, needed the most epochs compared to the others. In this case, however, the opposite was true: it needed only 28 epochs to train, compared to the models trained with the amplitude-phase pair and mask, which required 44 and 45 epochs for the training.

When comparing the three models on the basis of a confusion matrix in Figure 6.8, it can be observed that in only one case was the spread between the two classes not reduced: the fluorescence model mispredicted twice as often as the original (4%) the samples belonging to the debris class as yeast. In addition, in roughly all cases, the number of misrecorded cases decreased by 6%, which is a significant improvement in prediction.

In conclusion, we can safely ascertain that training models with fluorescent data have improved prediction accuracy in all cases. In the above experiments, we used only a scalar value to indicate the presence of fluorescence for each object. In future experiments, it

Figure 6.5: Accuracy of trained models for imbalanced training data

Figure 6.6: Loss function comparison with the three best models for imbalanced training sets

is worthwhile to examine the effect of providing the entire fluorescent image within the ROI belonging to each object. The expectation is that it will further improve accuracy and precision as it has more structural information embedded compared to a single scalar value to prevent misclassifications of (typically) dead yeasts.

Figure 6.7: F-score of trained models for imbalanced training data

Figure 6.8: Comparison of the three best models for imbalanced training data using a confusion matrix

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In this thesis, I investigated whether the accuracy of classification of individual objects by deep neural networks in images of samples containing microorganisms suspended in liquid taken with a digital holographic microscope can be improved by adding information from a fluorescent channel.

Digital holographic microscopy allows volumetric imaging of sparse suspensions, reconstruction of the focal plane of the suspended objects, and their automatic classification using machine learning algorithms. Due to the finite resolution of the imaging, classification based on morphology has limitations. The performance of classification is significantly degraded if the proportion of objects belonging to each class is imbalanced. Also due to limited resolution, the detection of small objects such as bacteria is difficult or not possible. Distinguishing between living and non-living organisms on holograms recorded by DHM is also very difficult, as there is minimal morphological difference between them. To overcome these problems, our research group has built a device that simultaneously records the holographic imaging of the field of view and can detect the autofluorescence emitted by the organisms on a separate imaging channel, as well as the fluorescence that occurs with a specific staining procedure.

For the experiments with unbalanced samples and training dataset, I used the algae species *Scenedesmus subspicatus*, and yeast species *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Illuminated with a 480nm laser, *Scenedesmus subspicatus* emits autofluorescence at 540nm, while *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, not containing chlorophyll, remains inert. I prepared a sample containing the two species in concentration 1:20 (SS and SC, respectively). Autofluorescence in images also helped annotation, as the annotating tool could prefilter objects to a certain degree based on average luminescence. The results of feeding autofluorescent information to the deep neural model were conclusive: compared to models

using only amplitude + phase, or amplitude + phase + (object mask with fluorescence information) as input, the accuracy of the classification has improved by 7%. Furthermore, the cross entropy loss has been reduced by a third (0.108) compared to the initial condition (0.307), which means that the prediction using autofluorescence is much better on test data than the performance of the model without fluorescence information.

For experiments to distinguish between living and non-living organisms, I prepared a sample containing live and dead *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (1:1). I used ethanol to render *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* inanimate. For my measurements, I used a simple staining procedure with FDA dye (allowing future automation with minimal sample preparation). FDA stains only living cells as they contain enzymes that break down molecules in FDA, and the end product emits fluorescence when illuminated. I have prepared a training database containing several thousands of labeled images. Similar to the imbalanced dataset case, I used three different deep neural models using amplitude + phase, amplitude + phase + object mask, and amplitude + phase + average fluorescent value within ROI as inputs, respectively. In the previous experiment, the results improved significantly by adding fluorescent information. Accuracy was highest for the fluorescent model (0.899, 0.906, and 0.956 respectively). Also for the F1 score, the model with the fluorescence value has the best result (0.961), performing almost 6% better than the other two models (0.909, 0.915). In both experiments, I used k-fold validation (k=5) to evaluate the performance of the different models.

In conclusion, we can safely ascertain that training models with fluorescent data have improved prediction accuracy in all cases.

Chapter 8

Summary

8.1. Tasks

In my thesis, my task was to use a fluorescence sample to improve the classification of objects on holograms captured by a digital holographic microscope. I created different databases containing not only the amplitude, phase and mask of the objects segmented from the holograms, but also the fluorescence signal of the object multiplied by the mask.

My first task was to fluorescently stain live and dead yeast cells within a sample to classify them by the detected fluorescence signal to create a training dataset.

The second task was to improve the classification of unbalanced classes. To do this, I used *Scenedesmus subspicatus* algae and yeast cells, taking advantage of the autofluorescence of the algae, thus making the procedure staining-free. The task was to prepare a sample containing approximately 1:20 algae to yeast cells ratio. This leads to a bias in the results in classification cases, but by having the trained models with fluorescence values assigned to objects, it was possible to recognize and accurately classify the objects sought.

8.2. Achievements

Using 5-fold cross-validation with different datasets in each case, a total of 30 models were trained with images containing a mixture of yeast and algae and yeast. Of these, 5-5 were trained with only the amplitude and phase images associated with the objects segmented after the holograms were acquired, another 5-5 were trained with masks to complement this data, while the last 5-5 had the average fluorescence value associated with the object detected during the measurements in addition to the data listed previously.

The comparisons show that there was no significant improvement in any of the models that had only the amplitude and phase and for which the mask was also available. The implication is that the mask does not provide any additional information beyond amplitude and phase to improve the image classification results.

However, in cases where fluorescence values detected during measurements were available, classification metrics were significantly improved for both live-dead yeast cell detection and unbalanced sample sets. Thus, it can be assumed that fluorescence as information can be an important part of solutions to various image classification problems for objects of interest that are either autofluorescent or can be specifically stained with the available dyes.

8.3. Plans for future work

In the above experiments we used only a scalar value to indicate the presence of fluorescence for each object. In future experiments it is worthwhile to examine the effect of providing the entire fluorescent image within the ROI belonging to each object. The expectation is that it will further improve accuracy and precision as it has more structural information embedded compared to a single scalar value to prevent misclassifications of (typically) dead yeasts.

The current experimental setup of the bimodal fluorescent/holographic microscope has its tradeoffs. The holographic optical path has a 7x magnification, adequate for objects in the 5-10 micron range. At this magnification, the microscope is able to image the whole volume, but for bacteria, which are smaller than 5 microns, the resolution is insufficient to distinguish them from similarly sized debris. In this case, the fluorescent signal would be essential for the detection of bacteria. However, due to its limited depth-of-field, the fluorescent path has only 1x magnification (the fluorescent signal quickly disperses out-of-focus objects), and this is insufficient to reliably detect bacteria. Therefore, as the next iteration of the bimodal microscope, a configuration is suggested with higher magnification for the fluorescent optical path, possibly with reduced sample depth, stronger illumination, etc.

In any case, the combination of holographic and fluorescent imaging seems a very promising direction for future product development.

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